

Serum Selenium: A Diagnostic Marker for Alzheimer's disease

Philomina Joicy V J^{#1}, Rajeshwari L^{*2}, Kavadi Naresh^{#3}

*#1, *2 JSS Medical College, JSS Academy of Higher Education and Research, Mysuru, India*

#3 JSS College of Physiotherapy, Mysuru

**2 corresponding author: Rajeshwari L*

Abstract- Oxidative stress resulting from free radicals released during metabolism is among the major pathophysiological processes responsible for Alzheimer's disease (AD). By being an integral part of an antioxidant defence system, Selenium plays a crucial role in combating oxidative damage. Alterations of selenium concentrations in plasma and brain are hypothesized to affect the neurodegenerative process and dietary supplementation has been proposed as adjunctive treatment. Studies of plasma selenium concentrations the world over, have yielded conflicting and inconsistent results. In this prospective Case – Control study, Plasma selenium level was estimated among 30 patients and 30 controls using Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICPMS). Selenium levels were found to be raised in AD patients compared to controls. we made a novel attempt to verify whether serum selenium can be a diagnostic marker for AD and it was found that the chance of not developing Alzheimer's disease lies within a narrow range of serum selenium between 55 µg /L and 106 µg /L. Community- Based validation with large population is recommended as geographical and racial difference are likely to affect selenium concentration in one's plasma.

Keywords: Selenium, Alzheimer's disease, oxidative stress, glutathione peroxidase, neurodegeneration

I. INTRODUCTION

Dementia affects 50 million people worldwide, the majority in middle and low-income countries. This number is projected by the WHO to reach 82 million in 2030 and 152 million by 2050. [1] In 2015, it was estimated that 4.1 million people in India had dementia and this is expected to double by 2030 and treble by 2050. [2, 3] According to official statistics, Alzheimer's disease ranked sixth among all causes of mortality in the US in 2019 and seventh in 2020 and 2021. Alzheimer's is still the fifth most common cause of mortality in the United States for people 65 and over, even after COVID-19 entered into the top ten causes of death. [4] In Kerala, a community survey of 2466 individuals, found that the age-adjusted prevalence of dementia to be 4.86% in people over 55 years and 6.44% in over 65-year-olds. [5] After follow-up of 8 years, researchers from the same group reported incidence rates for Alzheimer's dementia of 11.67 per 1000 person-years for those over 55 years and 15.54 for those ≥65 years. [6] These statistics provide convincing evidence that dementia, already a major public health problem, is expected to worsen in coming decades. The preponderance of dementia cases are constituted by Alzheimer's disease (AD), together with vascular dementia. Often Alzheimer and vascular pathology occur in combination. [7] AD is characterised by atrophy predominantly involving the medial temporal and parietal lobe and histopathologically by neuronal loss, β-amyloid plaque accumulation and neurofibrillary tangles caused by deposits of hyperphosphorylated tau protein. [8, 9, 10] Multiple factors including genetics, lifestyle, diet and exercise contribute to the etiopathogenesis of AD but oxidative stress plays a major role. Free radicals like reactive oxygen species (ROS) and nitrogen species (NOS) released during metabolism, react with lipids, proteins, nucleic acids, and other molecules to cause tissue damage. [11] Cells have defence mechanisms including antioxidant molecules and enzymes, to prevent or repair oxidative damage caused by ROS but increase in free radicals or decreased antioxidant defence can exacerbate oxidative stress. The brain is particularly vulnerable to oxidative damage since its antioxidant system is relatively deficient. [8]

Selenium, an essential micronutrient, is vital to the antioxidant network and it has been hypothesized that alteration in selenium concentrations could affect cellular defences against oxidative stress in the brain and influence the pathogenesis of AD. As selenocysteine, selenium is a component of the enzymes glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and thioredoxin reductase which are powerful free radical scavengers responsible for reducing and detoxifying hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). Selenoprotein P (SeP), a selenium transport protein, is thought to function as an antioxidant in extracellular space. High concentrations of SeP in the brain suggest an important physiological role. SeP immunoreactivity has been shown to co-localize with amyloid-β plaques and neurofibrillary tangles in post-mortem tissue from Alzheimer patients. [12] Variations in selenium level in blood and brain have been postulated to affect the antioxidant defence mechanisms, thereby influencing the pathogenesis and progression of neurodegenerative diseases including AD. Since studies of plasma selenium concentration in AD patients are few, especially from India, and have yielded conflicting results, this study aimed to evaluate status of plasma selenium in AD patients in coastal region of Kerala and to verify whether serum selenium can be a credible diagnostic marker to predict the risk for Alzheimer's disease.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. SAMPLE SELECTION

This Case – Control study was conducted in the department of Neurology, Little Flower Hospital and Research Centre, Angamaly, Kerala on a total of 60 subjects; categorized equally in case and control group. Sampling Procedure was Purposive sampling. Patients in the age group 40-90 years diagnosed with AD in the Neurology Department of the hospital and healthy individuals in the same age group to serve as controls, were recruited after obtaining voluntary, written, informed consent.

Subjects suffering from any major illness and those on selenium-containing supplements were excluded. Participants those who are pregnant and lactating were excluded.

B. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The present study was approved by institutional ethical committee of Little Flower Hospital and Research Centre, Angamaly.

C. METHODOLOGY

Participants were sorted out for the study after obtaining Informed Consent Letter. Demographic and clinical data was entered into a structured proforma. Outpatient AD patients and any age- matched controls were selected. For blood analysis, 2ml of blood was drawn using sterile techniques in EDTA tubes and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The plasma collected in micro vials was refrigerated at -40°C . Estimation of serum element concentration was estimated using ICP- MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma – Mass Spectrometry) technology.

D. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The outcome variable we considered was serum selenium level. All data were entered into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 20.0 version) for analysis. Comparison of means between the cases and controls was done using the Independent sample T- test and the range of serum selenium level to consider selenium as a biomarker was found by plotting ROC curve. P-value of 0.05 or less was interpreted as significant for the analysis.

III. RESULTS

The present study was conducted on total of 60 subjects including 30 cases and 30 age matched controls belonging to the age group of 40 - 90 years. Gender distribution in case and control group were 17 male and 13 female and 18 male and 12 female respectively. The mean age of subjects and control was 70.80 ± 6.059 years and 59.20 ± 8.015 years respectively. The duration of symptoms among the patient group ranged from 0 – 8 years. Out of the 30 subjects, 10 have their duration of symptoms between 0-2 years, 7 were between 2- 4 years, and 10 were in 4-6 years. Only 3 have their symptoms duration between 6-8 years.

Table 1 shows that the mean serum selenium was 110.83 ± 39.67 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in patient group and 100.07 ± 17.94 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in controls. The difference in mean observed was not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$) even though the selenium level seems high in Alzheimer's patients than normal population.

The statistical analysis by plotting ROC curve as given in Figure 1 showed that if the serum selenium level is less than 55 $\mu\text{g/L}$ or if more than 106 $\mu\text{g/L}$, there is possibility of Alzheimer's disease which is significantly predicted with 70% sensitivity and 66.7% specificity. (Table 2)

TABLE 1
COMPARISON OF SERUM SELENIUM LEVELS IN CASE AND CONTROLS

Group	n	Serum selenium ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	P Value
		Mean \pm SD	
Alzheimer's disease group	30	110.83 ± 39.67	0.181
Control group	30	100.07 ± 17.94	

There was no statistically significant difference in mean serum selenium level between case and control group ($P \text{ Value} > 0.05$)

Figure 1: ROC curve to assess the cut-off of serum selenium level to diagnose Alzheimer’s disease

TABLE 2
ASSESSMENT OF WHETHER SERUM SELENIUM CAN BE A DIAGNOSTIC MARKER FOR ALZHEIMER’S DISEASE

AUC	Cut-off Value		Significance (P Value)	Sensitivity	Specificity
	Minimum	Maximum			
0.718	0.055	0.106	0.004	70%	66.7%

The cut off value obtained is statistically significant, (P Value < 0.05)

IV. DISCUSSION

As with all neurodegenerative diseases, the genesis and progression of AD depends on multiple factors. Except in families where the disease has been linked to a single inherited gene, dissection of the interlinked genetic and environmental factors in causation of the disease is complicated. Regardless of the initiating insult, the integral presence of selenium in the antioxidant defence mechanism of the body has generated the hypothesis that variations in plasma and tissue selenium levels could affect the progression of AD and other neurodegenerative conditions. So far, many studies have been conducted in finding the association between one’s selenium status and development of AD.

Both selenium deficiency and toxicity have been reported to be linked to neurodegeneration. AD has been associated with decreased selenium concentration in brain homogenates compared to controls and the APOE ε4 allele correlated with lower total selenium levels in the temporal cortex and a higher concentration of soluble selenium. [13] On the other hand, selenium treatment has triggered apoptotic degeneration in a human neuronal cell line in vitro, suggesting that excess environmental exposure to selenium may represent a risk factor for neurodegenerative disease. [14] Studies of selenium levels across the world have reported inconsistent and often conflicting results with significant variation among populations. [15, 16] A Swedish study showed high plasma levels of selenium and other metals in AD [23] while the levels were not significantly different from the normal population in studies from Coimbatore, India and France. [17, 18] *Cardoso et al.*, found low dietary levels of selenium in AD patients from Brazil compared to controls with corresponding low levels of plasma, erythrocyte and nail selenium. [19] They also reported that selenium levels declined with advancing age. [8] These findings were not replicated by *Cardoso et al* in Australian patients who had adequate dietary selenium intake. Erythrocyte selenium levels were, however, found to be low in patients with AD. [20, 21] A low median level of selenium and high median level of inorganic arsenic were reported to be associated with significant AD risk in Taiwan. [22] A later study from Brazil, found no significant difference in selenium level but higher concentrations of copper and iron in AD. [23] Levels of selenium in patients with AD from Kerala have not previously been reported. In our study we observed that higher levels of serum selenium were found in AD patients, when compared with controls but the difference did not reach statistical significance.

Vinceti et al have questioned the reliability of the case-control design in assessing the role of selenium in AD. In a case-control study, AD risk was inversely correlated with inorganic selenium and with the selenoprotein P-bound organic form but directly correlated with other organo- selenium species suggesting compensatory selenoprotein upregulation following oxidative stress. A previous cohort study with a partially overlapping participant population had suggested an increased AD risk associated with inorganic selenium but this was not replicated in the case-control study. [24] Statistical attempts to resolve the issue through

meta-analysis have concluded that plasma, RBC, CSF and brain tissue selenium concentration is lower in AD patients as compared to controls and that this decrease in selenium had direct correlation with an antioxidant enzyme, the GPx. [25]

Working on the hypothesis that insufficient supply of selenium to antioxidant enzymes in the brain, may contribute to AD and that oral supplementation may slow neurodegeneration. *Cardoso et al* found that supranutritional selenium supplementation was well tolerated and yielded a significant but variable increase in CSF selenium, distributed across selenoproteins and inorganic species. [26] However, dietary selenium supplementation in AD has also been the subject of mixed reviews. *Aaseth et al* suggest that selenium supplementation for patients with MCI may be useful in preventing progression to AD [27] while *Loef et al* conclude that the evidence only allows 'speculation on a potential preventive relevance'. [28]

Selenium levels are affected by selenium content of the diet which, in turn, is influenced by the soil content, geographical location, seasonal changes, protein content and food processing. [16] The normal concentrations can therefore vary in different human populations. Seafoods and organ meats are rich dietary sources of selenium, which is also present in muscle meats, dairy products, cereals and other grains. [29] Since these foods are staples of the Kerala population, low dietary levels of selenium would not be expected to be a risk factor for the genesis and progression of neurodegenerative diseases in the state.

AD biomarker should serve as a diagnostic tool in clinical practice to allow early and presymptomatic identification of patients with AD, and to aid disease prevention programmes. Measuring biomarkers for brain diseases in the blood poses, a number of challenges that demand sensitive and specific assays and careful validation work. Brain-derived biomarkers are typically present at relatively low concentrations in the blood because of the blood-brain barrier preventing free passage of molecules between the CNS and blood compartments. [30]

A multivariate model built by profiling concentrations of six essential elements i.e. manganese, iron, copper, zinc, selenium and calcium and their ratios, was reported to discriminate AD patients from healthy controls with over 90% accuracy.[31] Our study is a novel attempt to determine the degree of reliability for serum selenium as a diagnostic marker for AD. From our small population study, we could significantly predict that if the serum selenium level is not within the range of 55 µg /L - 106 µg /L, there is a high possibility of Alzheimer's disease. Thus suggesting both selenium deficiency and toxicity can be a probable potential factors to develop AD. Even though, to fix serum selenium as a consistent biomarker for first-line screening for AD, further validation in a community- based setting is advised, as serum selenium concentration is inclined to change with geographical and racial differences.

V. CONCLUSION

Alarming rise in incidence rate for Alzheimer's disease provide convincing evidence that dementia, already a major public health problem, is expected to worsen in coming decades. Selenium, an essential micronutrient, is vital to the antioxidant network and it has been hypothesized that alteration in its concentrations could affect cellular defences against oxidative stress in the brain and influence the pathogenesis of AD. Levels of selenium in patients from AD with Kerala have not previously been reported. Using a prospective case-control design, we found higher levels of serum selenium in AD patients when compared with controls but the difference did not reach statistical significance. The present study is a novel attempt to determine the degree of reliability for serum Selenium as diagnostic marker for AD. And with significance, we discovered that chance of not developing Alzheimer's disease lies within a narrow range of serum selenium between 55 µg /L and 106 µg /L. Therefore before suggesting selenium supplementation as therapeutic intervention for AD, geographical and racial differences has to be taken in consideration. Further validation in a community- based setting is advised with larger sample size, to fix serum selenium as a consistent biomarker for first-line screening for AD.

REFERENCES

- [1] Dementia [Internet]. Who.int. 2017 [cited 10 June 2020]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/en/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/dementia>
- [2] Prince M, Wimo A, Guerchet M, Ali Gemma-Claire, Wu Yu-Tzu, Prina M. World Alzheimer Report 2015 - The Global Impact of Dementia : An Analysis of Prevalence, Incidence, Cost and Trends. London: Alzheimer's disease International (ADI); 2015.
- [3] Shaji KS, Jotheeswaran AT, Girish N, et al. Dementia India Report 2010: Prevalence, Impact, Costs and Services for Dementia. Alzheimer's & Related Disorders Society of India. New Delhi: ARDSI; 2010.
- [4] 2022 Alzheimer's disease facts and figures. (2022). Alzheimer's & dementia: the journal of the Alzheimer's Association, 18(4), 700–789. <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.12638>
- [5] Mathuranath PS, Cherian PJ, Mathew R, et al. Dementia in Kerala, South India: prevalence and influence of age, education and gender. Int J Geriatr Psychiatry. 2010; 25(3):290-297.
- [6] Mathuranath PS, George A, Ranjith N, et al. Incidence of Alzheimer's disease in India: a 10 years follow-up study. Neurol India. 2012; 60(6):625-630.
- [7] Sacuiu SF. Dementias. Handb Clin Neurol. 2016; 138:123-151.
- [8] Cardoso BR, Ong TP, Jacob-Filho W, Jaluul O, Freitas MI, Cozzolino SM. Nutritional status of selenium in Alzheimer's disease patients. Br J Nutr. 2010; 103:803–806.
- [9] Levenson RW, Sturm VE, Haase CM. Emotional and behavioral symptoms in neurodegenerative disease: A model for studying the neural bases of psychopathology. Annual review of clinical psychology. 2014; 10:581-606.

- [10] Nussbaum RL, Ellis EC. Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease. *N Engl J Med*. 2003; 348:1356-1364.
- [11] Huang WJ, Zhang X, Chen WW. Role of oxidative stress in Alzheimer's disease. *Biomedical reports*. 2016; 4(5):519–522.
- [12] Bellinger FP, He QP, Bellinger MT, et al. Association of selenoprotein p with Alzheimer's pathology in human cortex. *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2008;15(3):465-472.
- [13] Cardoso BR, Hare DJ, Lind M, et al. The APOE ε4 Allele Is Associated with Lower Selenium Levels in the Brain: Implications for AD. *ACS Chem Neurosci*. 2017;8(7):1459-1464.
- [14] Maraldi T, Riccio M, Zamboni L, Vinceti M, De Pol A, Hakim G. Low levels of Selenium compounds are selectively toxic for human neuron cell line through ROS/RNS increase and apoptotic process activation. *Neurotoxicology*. 2011;32:180- 187.
- [15] Office of Dietary Supplements - Selenium [Internet]. ods.od.nih.gov. 2020 [cited 10 June 2020]. Available from: <https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/Selenium-HealthProfessional/>
- [16] Navarro-Alarcon M, Cabrera-Vique C. Selenium in food and the human body: a review, *Sci Total Environ*. 2008;400:115-141.
- [17] Krishnan S, Rani P. Evaluation of selenium, redox status and their association with plasma amyloid/tau in AD. *Biol Trace Elem Res*. 2014;158(2):158-165.
- [18] Ceballos-Picot I, Merad-Boudia M, Nicole A, et al. Peripheral antioxidant enzyme activities and Selenium in elderly subjects and in dementia of Alzheimer's type--place of the extracellular glutathione peroxidase. *Free Radic Biol Med*. 1996;20(4):579-587.
- [19] Cardoso BR, Ong TP, Jacob-Filho W, et al. Glutathione peroxidase 1 Pro198Leu polymorphism in Brazilian Alzheimer's disease patients: relations to the enzyme activity and to Selenium status. *J Nutrigenet Nutrigenomics*. 2012;5(2):72-80.
- [20] Cardoso BR, Szymlek-Gay EA, Roberts BR, et al. Selenium Status Is Not Associated with Cognitive Performance: A Cross-Sectional Study in 154 Older Australian Adults. *Nutrients*. 2018;10(12):1847.
- [21] Cardoso BR, Hare DJ, Bush AI, et al. Selenium Levels in Serum, Red Blood Cells, and Cerebrospinal Fluid of Alzheimer's disease Patients: A Report from the Australian Imaging, Biomarker & Lifestyle Flagship Study of Ageing (AIBL). *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2017;57(1):183-193.
- [22] Yang YW, Liou SH, Hsueh YM, et al. Risk of Alzheimer's disease with metal concentrations in whole blood and urine: A case-control study using propensity score matching. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol*. 2018;356:8-14.
- [23] Vaz FNC, Fermino BL, Haskel MVL, et al. The Relationship between Copper, Iron, and Selenium Levels and Alzheimer Disease. *Biol Trace Elem Res*. 2018;181(2):185- 191.
- [24] Vinceti M, Michalke B, Malagoli C, et al. Selenium and Selenium species in the etiology of Alzheimer's dementia: The potential for bias of the case-control study design. *J Trace Elem Med Biol*. 2019; 53:154-162.
- [25] Reddy VS, Bukke S, Dutt N, Rana P, Pandey AK. A systematic review and meta-analysis of the circulatory, erythrocytic and CSF selenium levels in Alzheimer's disease: A metal meta-analysis (AMMA study-I). *J Trace Elem Med Biol*. 2017;42:68–75.
- [26] Cardoso BR, Roberts BR, Malpas CB et al. Supranutritional Sodium Selenate Supplementation Delivers Selenium to the Central Nervous System: Results from a Randomized Controlled Pilot Trial in Alzheimer's disease. *Neurotherapeutics*. 2019; 16:192–202.
- [27] Aaseth J, Alexander J, Björklund G et al. Treatment strategies in AD: a review with focus on Selenium supplementation. *Biometals*. 2016; 29:827–839.
- [28] Loeff M, Schrauzer GN, Walach H. Selenium and AD: a systematic review. *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2011; 26(1):81-104.
- [29] Sunde RA. Se. In: Ross AC, Caballero B, Cousins RJ, Tucker KL, Ziegler TR, eds. *Modern Nutrition in Health and Disease*. 11th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2012:225-237.
- [30] Zetterberg H, Blalock EM. Blood-based molecular biomarkers for Alzheimer's disease. *Molecular brain*. 2019; 12(1):26.
- [31] Paglia G, Miedico O, Cristofano A, Vitale M, Angiolillo A, Chiaravalle AE, et al. Distinctive Pattern of Serum Elements During the Progression of Alzheimer's Disease. *Sci Rep*. 2016; 6:22769.